

Introduction

To guide me through the experiment and not to make any mistakes I will follow a script.

Thank you for taking part in this evaluation session for the DJeye interface. During this session we will need to record some video material that will later be analyzed. The transcript of our conversation could be published in pseudonymized form. If you agree, I ask you to sign this informed consent document.

[Sign the consent document]

During this experiment you will use DJeye, a DJ interface for mixing audio tracks controlled through your eyes, looking at the screen.

The experiment will take place in several stages. During which:

- We will calibrate the eye-tracker for your eyes
- I will briefly explain how interaction by eye tracking works
- You will try to use the interface on your own
- You will perform some guided tasks, which will gradually lead you to learn how the interface works
- You will answer a final questionnaire

We are interested in evaluating the design of the tool, to understand how it will be received and used by the average user, and to gather your opinions. During the experiment, I will often ask you to think aloud or express an opinion. It will help us if you respond as naturally, truthfully and honestly as possible. The more *brutally honest* your answers are, the more they will help us improve the design. Therefore, do not be afraid to make positive or negative judgments. You will also not be evaluated in any way by this experiment, it will not affect your college career in any way, and do not feel pressured in any way by the required exercises. Remember that you can refuse to perform any task or decide to take a break or withdraw from the experiment at any time.

Do you have any questions before you start?

Are you ready?

[OBS recording start]

Pre-questionnaire

Now I ask you to answer these brief introductory open questions:

[annotate answers]

1. What kind of experience do you have with DJ consoles/controllers? Do you know the terminology of these interfaces (slider, deck, crossfader, filter, seek track/needle drop, loop)?
2. What kind of experience do you have with DJing software?
3. From 1 to 7, where 1 means "very little" and 7 means "very much": how much interest do you have in DJing interfaces?
4. From 1 to 7: How much experience do you have with eye-trackers?

Basics

With the eye tracker you can control the cursor as if it were a mouse. While you are using the interface the cursor will be hidden, however the buttons will light up to give you visual feedback.

There are two ways you can interact with the buttons:

- Closing the left eye will correspond to a click
- By closing your right eye and moving your left eye gaze up or down a few inches, you will perform a dragging action

[hand-guided test to let people understand how the interaction method works]

keep in mind that during drag and drop, as soon as you open your right eye the interaction will stop immediately

DJeye is a controller, so it is comparable to a physical controller. To play it requires underlying DJ software: MIXXX, of which you will only see the library

The purpose of this experiment is to evaluate the interface and not to perform perfect mixes. so even if you don't "mix like a pro" it's perfectly fine

The list of tracks you will be able to mix is default.

- They have similar BPM (around 125). They will be synchronized automatically at the same time to be easy to mix;
- Quantization is active, so the beats will always be temporally synchronized.
 - tracks resume playback when they reach the end

I will give you a couple of minutes to familiarize yourself with the tracks. I suggest you pick three in particular, and listen to parts of them.

Go ahead and tell me the tracks you want to listen to, and I'll upload them and play them for you.

[2 minutes]

[controller reset]

[controller test]

[give headphones to subject and have him place one ear up and one ear down]

[adjust volume in headphones]

Calibration

We will now proceed to calibrate the eye tracker for your eyesight.

Keep your eyes wide open, you can move with your head if necessary. focus well on the pellets to have optimal calibration.

[Calibration procedure]

Now let's do a small test to see if the cursor placement is accurate, if so repeat the calibration

[test]

Free phase

[note]

I will now "abandon you to yourself" for a short period of 8 minutes. During this time, I will give you no indication of how the interface will work. Try to navigate the interface, to guess each of these commands what it is for, and how it works.

In the meantime, I ask you to "think out loud": describe to me, speaking, as naturally as possible, what you want to do and what you are thinking, commenting freely, even with your emotions.

For example, "I'm trying to figure out how this button works, now I'm going to try to click it. I understand that it is for doing this..."

During this stage I will not be able to help you or give you guidance on how it works. You can pretend that I am not there or that I don't know how to help you at all, but remember to "think out loud."

Are you ready?

[8 min]

[do not help them unless they are really in trouble, e.g., software crashes or similar events]

Task phase

[calibration check]

[controller reset]

Stop.

We will now do a phase where I will ask you to do some specific tasks. During this phase I will guide you to explore the interface in a guided way, in what will be a kind of "tutorial."

We will have no time limit, but if I see that you will struggle to perform a task I may decide to move on. Likewise, you may decide to refuse to run a task for any reason.

I ask that you stick precisely to my requests, so don't perform any more tasks on your own. don't worry, eventually there will be a final free phase where you can do whatever you like

Remember that when I ask you to click, it will mean that you will have to do a left wink. When I ask you to drag, it will mean you have to do a right wink and move your gaze up to increase, or down to decrease.

As you may have noticed, the interface is divided into two decks, which enlarge when your gaze passes over them. In the center of each deck is a Play button, while around it are other sliders that perform other functions. Between the two decks, you find the crossfader at the bottom and the track selector at the top.

Relax and take your time to perform each task. If you can, comment by expressing opinions such as "easy, difficult, intuitive, strange, etc." also this time think out loud and tell me whatever is on your mind.

Are you ready?

Task list

Loads a track into the right deck. To do this:

1. click on the button in the center of the interface that symbolizes a list
2. choose a track by clicking the up/down directional arrows
3. click the R button to load the track to the right channel

Play the right track by clicking on the play button on the right deck

To begin headphone listening to the right track, click on the right headphone button

choose a point on the right track from which you want to start playback by dragging the track seek slider, with the two arrows symbol

Raise the volume of the right track by dragging the right volume slider, with the speaker symbol

To stop headphone listening to the right track, click on the right headphone button

Load a track in the left deck

Play the left track by clicking on the left play button

To begin headphone listening to the left track, click on the left headphone button

Choose a point on the left track from which you want to start playback by dragging the track seek slider, with the two arrows symbol

To stop headphone listening to the left track, click on the left headphone button

Lower the value of the filter of the left track almost completely by dragging down the slider with the knob symbol

Raise the volume of the left track by dragging the left volume slider, with the speaker symbol

Perform a crossfade by dragging the crossfader all the way to the left

Returns the left channel filter to its center value

stops the execution of the right track by clicking on the play button

Turn the volume of the right track down to 0 by dragging down the right volume slider, with the speaker symbol

loads a track in the right deck

play the right track by clicking on the right play button

To begin headphone listening to the right track, click on the right headphone button

choose a point on the right track from which you want to start playback by dragging the track seek slider, with the two arrows symbol

Activates the 2-bar loop by clicking on the left loop slider

Raise the volume of the right track as desired by dragging the right volume slider

Perform a crossfade by dragging the crossfader to the middle

To stop headphone listening to the right track, click on the right headphone button

Decrease the value of the left loop by one notch by dragging on the loop slider down one step

Complete the crossfade by sliding the crossfader to the right

stop playback of the left track by clicking on the left play button

Turn the volume of the left track down to 0 by dragging the left volume slider

Position the crossfader in the center, dragging the crossfader

Turn the volume of the right track down to 0 by dragging the right volume slider

[notes]

[max 30s for each task]

Free phase

[calibration check]

[controller reset]

You will now have a few minutes to freely "play" with the tool, using the knowledge you have learned about how the interface works. I ask you again this time to "think aloud" describe to me, speaking, as naturally as possible, what you want to do and what you are thinking, commenting freely. also describe to me emotions, feelings, what seems to be working or not working, what you would like to do but it is not possible for you to do.

[5-10 min]

(At the end):

Can you make some brief and general comments about the instrument?

[stop registrazione OBS]

Final questionnaire

Now I am going to ask you to fill out a questionnaire, in which we are going to analyze different points of the experience. For each question, feel free to comment and justify

your answer. Every comment and information is valuable to us. Remember to be as honest as possible.

[questionnaire]